

Nitration. Part II.* Simultaneous Diazotisation and Nitration of Aromatic Amino-Compounds.

BY

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A few cases of simultaneous diazotisation and nitration have been noticed where the active agent used for the purpose was nitrous acid. 2:6-Dinitro-cresol was obtained by treating 2-nitro-*p*-toluidine with an excess of nitrous acid by Knecht (*Annalen*, 1882, 215, 90). 2:6-Dinitro-cresol was produced by the action of nitrous acid on *p*-toluidine (Martius and Wichelhaus, *Ber.*, 1869, 2, 207). 5-Brom-3-nitro-cresol was obtained along with brom-*o*-cresol by the action of nitrous acid on brom-*o*-toluidine (Claus and Jackson, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1881, (ii), 38, 32; Wroblewski, *Annalen*, 1873, 168, 165).

A systematic investigation of the subject was carried on by Deninger (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1889, (ii), 40, 296) who tried the action of nascent nitrous acid (obtained in the reacting mixture by the action of acids on sodium nitrite) on various amino-compounds and obtained nitro-phenolic compounds. He succeeded thus in getting *o*- and *p*-nitro-phenols from aniline, *o*- and *p*-nitro-cresols from *o*-toluidine and a nitro-cresol from *p*-toluidine, dinitro-diphenol and

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dinitro-di-cresol from benzidine and toluidine, β -nitro- α -naphthol and dinitro-naphthol from α -naphthylamine, and α -nitro- β -naphthol from β -naphthylamine. In attempting to prepare *p*-bromphenol from *p*-brom-aniline nitrate, through the intervention of the diazo-reaction, Olivieri (*Gazzetta*, 1884, 14, 459) employed nitrous anhydride from As_2O_3 and HNO_3 and succeeded in getting nitro-brom-phenol which result he attributed to the use of HNO_3 of too high specific gravity and to the production of NO_2 therefrom.

Attempts have been made in this paper to bring about nitration and diazotisation in one operation by means of nitrous gases produced by the action of concentrated nitric acid on arsenious oxide. A number of amino-compounds have been tried and a good yield of nitro-phenolic compounds in a fair state of purity has been obtained in several cases. This method appears to be quite suitable for the preparation of some of these nitro-compounds in the laboratory.

Thus from aniline 2:5-dinitro-phenol, from *p*-nitraniline 2:4-dinitro-phenol, from *p*-chloro-aniline 2:3-dinitro-4-chloro-phenol, from *p*-brom-aniline 4-brom-3-nitro-phenol, from *s*-tribrom-aniline *s*-tribrom-dinitro-phenol, from *o*-toluidine 4-nitro-*o*-cresol, from 5-brom-*o*-toluidine 5-brom-3-nitro-*o*-cresol, from *p*-toluidine 2:6-dinitro-cresol, from *m*-xylydine 6-nitro-*m*-xylenol, from *o*-anisidine *p*-nitro-phenol-*o*-methyl ether, from benzidine a mono-nitro-phenolic compound, from *o*-amido-salicylic acid nitro-proto-catechuic acid, from *o*-amido-benzoic acid 3-nitro-salicylic acid, from *m*-amido-benzoic acid 5-nitro-3-hydroxybenzoic acid, from α -naphthylamine 2-nitro- α -naphthol, from β -naphthylamine 1-nitro- β -naphthol have been obtained, whilst *o*-nitraniline produces no definite product and *m*-nitraniline gives yellow shining plates, the nature of which is not yet determined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The usual procedure in carrying out these experiments has been to dissolve the hydrochloride of the base in water or the base itself in hydrochloric acid solution, or if it is not very soluble, to keep it in suspension, cool the solution or suspended mass in a freezing mixture below 0° and then pass nitrous gases for about half an hour (or less, if gases are no more absorbed), allow the reacting substances to stand for some time, in some cases overnight, and then heat on a water-bath for half an hour, allow them to cool, remove the crystals separated, recrystallise them from rectified spirit and identify them by determination of melting point and the percentage of nitrogen.

<i>Starting material.</i>	<i>Product.</i>
(2g. was taken in each case.)	
Aniline hydrochloride	... Dinitro-phenol (1.5 g.).
<i>o</i> -Nitraniline dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... No definite product.
<i>m</i> -Nitraniline dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... Yellow shining plates, extremely explosive.
<i>p</i> -Nitraniline dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... Dinitro-phenol (1.5 g.).
<i>p</i> -Chloraniline dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... 2:3-Dinitro-4-chlorophenol (1.5 g.).
<i>p</i> -Brom-aniline dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... 4-Brom-2-nitrophenol, yellow plates, m. p. 89° (0.4 g.).
<i>s</i> -Tribrom-aniline.	... <i>s</i> -Tribrom-dinitrophenol, yellow plates, m. p. 195° (0.4 g.).
<i>o</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride.	... 4-nitro- <i>o</i> -cresol (2.1 g.).
5-Brom- <i>o</i> -toluidine dissolved in hydrochloric acid.	... 5-Brom-3-nitro- <i>o</i> -cresol (2.5 g.)
<i>p</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride.	... 2:6-Dinitro- <i>p</i> -cresol (1.3 g.).
<i>m</i> -Xylidine in hydrochloric acid solution.	... 6-Nitro- <i>m</i> -xylenol (1.8 g.).

<i>Starting material.</i>	<i>Product.</i>
(2g. was taken in each case.)	
<i>o</i> -Anisidine in hydrochloric acid ... solution.	A small quantity of <i>p</i> -nitrophenol- <i>o</i> -methyl ether, brownish black plates, m. p. 53°.
Benzidine hydrochloride. ...	A mono-nitro-derivative, m. p. 104° (1.9 g.).
<i>o</i> -Amido-saliicylic acid in hydrochloric acid solution. ...	Nitro-protocatechuic acid, decomposing above 200° (1.2 g.).
<i>o</i> -Amido-benzoic acid in hydrochloric acid solution. ...	3-Nitro-saliicylic acid (1.8 g.).
<i>m</i> -Amido-benzoic acid in hydrochloric acid solution. ...	5-Nitro-3-hydroxy-benzoic acid, pale yellow needles, m. p. 166° (1.2 g.).
α -Naphthylamine in hydrochloric acid solution. ...	2-Nitro- α -naphthol, deep reddish-brown crystals, m. p. 126-127° (1.9 g.).
β -Naphthylamine in hydrochloric acid solution. ...	1-Nitro- β -naphthol, thin red crystals, m. p. 104° (1.9 g.).

In the case of aniline hydrochloride, the reaction is vigorous and the solution is coloured deep green, changing to deep red on standing. Shining yellow plate-like crystals (m. p. 104°) are obtained from rectified spirit (Found: N=15.65. $C_6H_5(NO_2)_2OH$ requires N=15.25 per cent.).

From *m*-nitraniline yellow shining thin plates of extremely explosive nature are obtained. This product is not yet identified.

With *p*-chloraniline, brownish yellow crust is formed, the solution turning deep yellow at the same time. On crystallisation long yellow needles, m. p. 70-71°, are obtained. (Found: N=12.99; Cl=16.29. $C_6H_4(OH)(NO)_2Cl$ requires N=12.81; Cl=16.05 per cent.).

With *o*-toluidine, the alcoholic solution is scratched with a glass rod before fine reddish-brown needles, m. p. 81-82°, are obtained. (Found: N=9.30. $C_6H_3(CH_3)(OH)NO_2$ requires N=9.17 per cent.).

From *p*-toluidine greenish-yellow plate-like crystals, m. p. 80-81°, are obtained. (Found: N=14.10. $C_6H_2(CH_3)(OH)(NO_2)_2$ requires N=14.15 per cent.).

With *m*-xylidine, the reaction is feeble and the solid product separates on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. Brown hygroscopic plates, m. p. 92°, are obtained.

With α - and β -naphthylamines, the reacting mixtures should not be heated on water-bath above 50°, else charring takes place. In both cases good yield (about 80 per cent. of the theory) of the nitro-derivatives is obtained.

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